

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TEWELDE BERHANE****FIRST NAME: AWET****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: RP 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 8)

THE NEED TO KNOW SKILLS OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The mastery of essay writing is an essential skill that a student of higher learning like me or a professional has to acquire. One may have the capacity to write, however, in the case of academic as well as professional essay writing at the international level there are some fundamental rules that need to be followed to write a good essay. In this first course pack, I have been able to identify the shortcomings I have in essay writing and equip myself with the necessary knowledge for the academic writings that are expected from me for my LLM course which I am taking with Euclid. I have been able to find that the ACA-401 course pack on essay writing provides the basics in academic essay writing. In this response paper, I shall attempt to elaborate the fundamentals of international essay writing.

2) ESSAY WRITING-THE BASICS

In writing an essay, the first step is to identify a question (an issue) that needs to be answered or a well-researched solution for a problem. A writer has to understand the question he has to answer very well. Before embarking on the process of writing, the writer should write down everything he knows about the topic (EUCLID 2015, 3). This helps the writer to brainstorm himself of what he (the masculine pronouns will also be applies to the feminine gender) already knows about the topic in question. He has to bear in mind that he should avoid procrastination and start writing as soon as possible.

Reading and conducting a thorough research on the available literatures is also necessary with the question in mind that the essay intends to answer. This could go on

until the writer completes writing the essay. While reading and researching for information and evidences to substantiate the arguments the writer should take notes and keep record of the references for proper citation thereof.

The writer needs to determine the question to be answered in the essay; analyze it properly; and then has to draw an initial plan on how to write the essay. When writing an academic or professional essay, he should try to persuade the reader that his proposition is correct by presenting a justified argument. The writer should attempt to define “key terms” to familiarize the reader with essential words or phrases that are included in the essay. An essay should be written in way to answer a specific question by raising a thesis statement which serves as a theme for the essay, justified by logically developed and convincing arguments.

In the beginning the essay should be in a draft form which eventually will be edited and refined to give it its final structure and substance (EUCLID 2015, 4). Basically, the essay should be structured in a form consisting: an introductory part in the beginning where the thesis is stated and a general outline of the essay to build the argument. Then follows the body of the essay where the thesis is discussed and supported by examples and evidences; and finally comes the conclusion part where the answer or the final finding of the essay is stated.

3) THE INGRIDIENTS FOR A GOOD ESSAY

a) Following an Academic Writing Style

In ordinary text communications, one can use contractions of words. However, one of the important lessons of this course pack was that when writing an academic essay I should avoid contractions such as: isn't – instead of- is not (EUCLID 2015, 39). Moreover, I have been able to take note that I should employ logical connectors like: “Moreover,” “Nevertheless,” and so forth at the beginning of sentences to maintain a smooth flow of my idea (EUCLID 2015, 40).

b) Proper Referencing

An important lesson that I have learnt from this course is a new technique of referencing known as the in-text-referencing apart from the use of footnotes used when one follows the list of works cited method of referencing to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 15). A writer should be very careful to give proper credit for the information he uses in his essay which is originally authored by other people. Failing to do so, may result in a severe consequence entailing penalty. Hence, proper citation is very a very important rule that has to be followed whether it is in the form of in-text citation or in the form a footnote. In doing so, the proper forms of citation rules should be observed. Moreover, I have been able to understand that signal phrases can also be used by a writer to indicate the author work which has been included in the essay (EUCLID 2019, 32).

4) THE NEED TO KNOW RULES OF THUMB FOR ESSAY WRITING

An academic paper has to be written in a manner that will enable the writer to communicate and justify his proposition. Hence, a writer has to put forward the premise he is to discuss in the first paragraph of his paper. In the following paragraphs and sections, the writer should specifically and critically address his thesis without including sentences or phrases that are irrelevant to the discussion.

I have been able to learn from this section of the course pack what the length of a sentence and a paragraph should be. To make the paper more comprehensible and appealing to the reader, the sentences and paragraphs should be short and filled with simple but rather descriptive words (EUCLID 2015, 43). I believe this will help me to avoid from writing a very long sentence or paragraph which might confuse the reader. I have taken note that every sentence should be constructed differently from the others to make the paper exciting to the reader. Moreover, if the paper is premised on the anti-thesis of another writer, the writer should objectively discuss his proposition and that of the original writer (EUCLID 2015, 44).

5) PROPER USE OF GRAMMAR AND PUNCTUATION

From my readings from the LIT-101 REVIEW note of this coursepack I have been able to refresh my previous lectures and capitalize on new grammatical rules that I have not thought of their effect when used in a sentence. A good command of grammar and the placement of the various punctuation marks of the English language are very crucial for a writer to properly and effectively express the information that is intended to be communicated to the reader. This is due to the fact that an improper use of grammar and the positioning of a punctuation mark in the wrong place in a sentence or a phrase results in giving a meaning that is totally different from that which is intended to be communicated by the author.

Certain uses of grammatical uses that were taught to us at school or by parents as proper might in some instances create confusion to the reader. Since, it is imperative that a writer expresses his idea as he intended, he should not be bound by grammar and punctuation uses that may imply a different meaning. Furthermore, he should always be careful not to manifest redundancy in the use of words.

6) WRITING STYLE

Apart from the notes which explain about the observance of proper grammar and punctuation, the lesson on the proper use of the various writing styles was an eye opener for me that are prescribed by different publishers or preferred by certain discipline or profession (EUCLID 2019, 52). It has enabled me to learn about the different writing

styles especially the Chicago Rules (Turabian) which is the more preferred one by Euclid. I have picked up from this note that a writing style helps to create consistency in the writing formats that writers have to follow in terms of font, use of language variety (UK or US English), heading arrangement and so forth. The use of a writing style is also beneficial in saving time for the writer to edit and proofread his paper.

7) BRITISH VS. AMERICAN ENGLISH IN ESSAYS

In English language there are different varieties in terms of spelling and grammar. However, the most widely used are that of the US and of the UK. When writing an essay, the spelling, punctuation use and the grammatical arrangement of words should be consistent throughout the essay. Due, to the various influencing factors, it should be noted that the US English is currently the most preferred language variety in the publication of different writings (EUCLID 2019, 54).

8) CONCLUSION

As a student of a master's degree program with the Euclid University, the different topics that were discussed under period one- ACA-401 coursepack have enabled me to understand and identify what kind of writing techniques I have to follow in professional as well as academic essays and dissertations. I believe that the lesson from this course pack will be an additional asset to the paper writing courses I have taken during my stay in the School of Law on other training programs I have participated.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>.

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